

DERIVED STAKEHOLDERS’ FUND UTILISATION MODEL FOR NIGERIAN PUBLIC HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (NPHEIS)

Adams O.U. Onuka, Monica N. Odinko and Babatunde Kassim Oladele

Institute of Education, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria

Email:ada.otuoze@gmail.com/moniquengozi@yahoo.com/oladelebat@gmail.com

(*orcidID*:<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3317-3966>)

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Abstract: *This paper studied the possibility of evolving Nigerian public higher education institutions’ {NPHEIs} stakeholders’ fund utilisation model for sustainable improved higher education provision. It examined one principal thematic question under some sub-themes. The qualitative approach was used. The population of the study was all public tertiary education institutions in Nigeria irrespective of whether their ownership is either national or sub-national. The country was classified along the six existing zones: Each type of higher institutions: colleges of education, polytechnics and universities was purposively selected from one randomly state from each zone provided at least one is owned by the national and the sub-national give 18 PHEIs, made up of six of each type of HEIs (903 respondents participated). Interview schedule and Focus group discussion {FGD} guide were used data which were qualitatively thematically analysed. The results showed that the stakeholders proposed three principal component-NPHEIs’ stakeholders’ model for participation in fund utilisation: They are namely, 1. Transparency and accountability with emphasis on mechanisms for transparency, accountability and internal control; 2. Monitoring and supervision with mechanisms for prudent practices, stakeholders’ involvement in fund management and records keeping, and monitoring oversight committees; and 3. Institutional fund managers’ high level financial discipline. It was concluded that a summit of stakeholders’ should be convened to consider and adapt the model for legislation and implementation. Recommendations were that all stakeholders led by the government should adapt the model for implementation for improved financial prudence, and the oversight over financial administration should by stakeholders’ representatives.*

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INTRODUCTION

The importance of providing the populace of any nation with higher education is viewed with all seriousness over the globe. This is because Higher Education provision is very pivotal to individual and national development. It is the sub-sector of the economy responsible for producing and providing high level human capital to drive national and indeed global development. This importance of the HE to any nations informs why it should be properly funded. However, there are two main facets to funding any institutions (education or otherwise): Provision and utilisation. Fund provided but not prudently utilised will amount to waste of resources its purpose may not be realised (Onuka, 2012, Bakkabulindi, 2005 and Kasozi, 2009). According to FRN (2013), higher or tertiary education is post-secondary education. Higher education is mainly provided by the following Higher education institutions in Nigeria: Polytechnics/Monotechnics, Colleges of Education and Universities. From the time of Babangida Military regime in Nigeria, in the mid-1980's and early 1990's, there had problem with the issue of funding Nigerian public higher education institutions (NPHEIs) sub-sector, which produces the bulk of high calibre human capital. Onuka (2017) found that even the little fund at the disposal of Public universities was not properly managed via spending on frivolities like travelling at the instance of government to just accompany a minister to

open a conference, which has no real impact on the running the institutions. The problem has continued to escalate till date. From 1992 to 2022, for instance there was hardly any year without industrial dispute between higher education institutions' unions and governments at both Federal and Sub-national levels, due to the poor teaching and learning conditions (Onuka, 2017). However, there were also disputes within each institution bothering on inappropriate utilisation of funds. This implies that even as there is the problem of inadequate funding of these institutions, there is also the challenge of imprudence in fund utilisation. Therefore, the problem of inappropriate utilisation of available fund must equally be addressed.

It is also pertinent to note that only 40% of the usually less than 10% of national budget that goes to education is given all federally owned higher education institutions (universities, polytechnics/monotechnics and colleges of education). Taking cognisance of this abysmal state funding, those dispensing the fund ought to prioritise their spending on priority necessities and relevant recurrent expenditure that would facilitate quality learning. Thus, the need to evolve a sustainable funding model to ensure that there is constant inflow of funds for use by NPHEIs by the various stakeholders. It will also ensure that available funds are prudently utilised. Such a model would allow stakeholders to have a say on how funds are

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sourced and utilised and also monitor the utilisation process. Onuka (2017) submitted that it is one thing to adequately provide fund for public universities, but it is another thing to ensure transparent and accountable utilisation. Thus, a fund utilisation monitoring system would ensure that embezzlement, misapplication, misappropriation and mismanagement of the available fund to NPHEIs are avoided and value for money is obtained by the stakeholders. If such a mechanism is in place the institutions can rest assured that stakeholders won't be weary in supporting with the appropriate level of funding as they would be encouraged to put their share because they are assured that it will be utilised for public good and the future of the succeeding generations assured. Having a fund utilisation model will easily expose incidences of malfeasance in the system and the trend could then be nipped in the bud and funds will be appropriately utilised for the purposes for which they are meant: public good. Onuka (2017) argued that for the success of fund utilisation model, there must workable budgeting system to guide the application of utilisation mechanism. Onuka (2011) had earlier observed that the two ways to sustaining adequate funding of the Nigerian public university system are through aggressive mobilisation and prudent utilisation. The latter will encourage and upscale fund provision from those from we seek such provision. Olatunji and Onuka (2024) argued that only availability of the right

quantum of funding and prudent application of it would raise educational standards anywhere in the world. Aregbeyen (2025) at a symposium in honour of Professor J.B. Babalola, advocated academic units' involvement in the application of funds, particularly in the sharing formula among the various layers of the University system, so that the Departments where the programmes are domiciled can run efficiently and effectively too. He also suggested restructuring the governance structure of the African University system, especially with regard to creating positions that duplicate functions, in order to minimise wastages. In the same vain, Ayeni (2025) argued at the same forum, that institutional financial managers, at the various layers of operation in the Nigerian higher education system, must be able to maintain self-fiscal discipline accountability, so that available funds are utilised for the purpose they were meant for.

Onuka (2012) equally suggested budgetary presentation to, and also implementation monitoring system by University Senates and other stakeholders within the university system to ensure that available funds are judiciously applied for efficiency and effectiveness of the sector. This can equally be extended to all other types of public HEIs in Nigeria. For Oralu & Oladele (2015), though it appeared the government has realised its mistakes and now welcomes and encourages participation of local communities, individuals and organisations to assist in funding education, it is yet to be

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practised. This is obvious from the fact that no such model has been put to use for funding the Nigerian public higher education system. They also posited that there was an urgent need to sensitise the Nigerian people to appreciate the need to adequately contribute to education financing. Such development will not be peculiar to Nigeria as Tanzania through her education authority has a model whereby she sources funds from stakeholders to augment the government's subvention to the sector (Tanzania Education Authority (TEA), undated). Onuoha (2013) advocated using well-managed internally generated revenue to augment whatever comes from the government to each institution in terms of revenue, implying that whatever is the source of the revenue, it is important that it is properly applied and efficiently too.

Okebukola (2015) had reported that a few studies by some Nigerian scholars showed that in the ten years before 2014, at no time, was allocation to education in Nigeria ever more than 2% of Gross National Product (GDP). Furthermore, Okebukola submitted that there were different funding models, such as performance-based funding model, contextualized formula-funding model, access-equity cost sharing model for public universities and host-proprietor-university-user-funding model. However, there is no any empirical evidence found to support the implementation of any of these model proposals in Nigeria. More so, the models did not consider utilisation

and monitoring model[s] for fund utilisation. Only proper utilisation of sourced fund would provide basis for further commitment by stakeholders, and that would also ensure the quality of outputs from these institutions. It must be noted that in some studies like the ones by Nabena, Eze, Rowe, Mohammed and Oni (2024) and Bamiro and Adedeji (2010), it can be inferred from their recommendations that inefficiency in fund utilisation in the education sector was highlighted. Thus, it is imperative for a study to propose an efficient way to administer the funds accruing to Nigerian Public Higher Education institutions. However, in Uganda, there seems to be a process of allocating specific amount to research and academic programme components of Makerere University, which tended to ensure prudence in financial administration (Onen, 2024).

However, it has also been discovered that those who are charged with managing fund in higher institutions in Nigeria are averse to financial transparency and would rather shroud their finances in secrecy than expose them to the public for scrutiny or even for research purpose as was experienced in the course of this research and was submitted by Oduwaiye (2014) and also affirmed by Ayodele (2025). Yet, without transparency and accountability it would be difficult for stakeholders to be willing to commit their financial resources to supporting institutions. There is the dearth of literature on available fund utilisation model either at the Federal or State owned Higher Education

Adams O.U. Onuka, Monica N. Odinko and Babatunde Kassim Oladele

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Institutions in Nigeria. Therefore, this study was designed to generate stakeholders' suggested sustainable fund utilisation model for the Nigerian public Higher Education Institutions (i.e. Universities, College of Education and Polytechnics/monotechnics that are owned by either State or Federal Government).

Research Question:

Consequently to address the identified problem of the non-existent of universal fund utilisation model, the following question was addressed in multiple sub-themes, and holistic model was brought out of these sub-themes:

1. What is the suggested stakeholders' participation in prudent fund utilisation model for NPHEIs?

METHODOLOGY

The design for this study was the qualitative approach based on thematic analysis. The choice of this approach was to enable the researchers derived a truly sustainable stakeholders' fund utilisation model from open-ended interactions with them, rather than a close-ended, guided responses determined by some persons apart from the respondents, whereas the model is expected to be entirely derived from the stakeholders, which is the uniqueness of the study. The population was the entire Nigerian public higher education institutions (federal and state). The current cluster of six geo-political zones was used for sampling basis. A state was randomly picked from each zone and each type of the higher

education institutions identified in the study were purposively selected on the basis of inclusion of at least one each of the three types of HEIs (University, Polytechnic and College of Education) and also on basis at least one of each by ownership of (federal and state) is included from each of the selected state. Thus, 18 HEIs were used in the study: 6 Universities, 6 Polytechnics and 6 Colleges. Stakeholders were classified as follows: Council members/POs; Deans/Directors/HoDs; Parents, staff and Students as well as community leaders, FBOs and CBOs, Alumni Association members and employers of labours through multi-stage procedure: zone, state, institution and stakeholders of diverse categories, while proportionate random, convenient and snowballing sampling techniques were used. Simple random was used in selecting the states, the purposive sampling was utilised in chosen key officers of the institutions, convenient sampling was made use of in selecting the Alumni Association members, FBOs, CBOs, and some other stakeholders while snowballing cum tracer were the sampling techniques for selecting the employers A total of 903 stakeholders in these institutions that participated in the study as stated above. The FGD and interview schedules were developed by the researchers and reviewed and content validated by ten experts in the field, whose comments were juxtaposed to form the items in the final instruments.

Adams O.U. Onuka, Monica N. Odinko and Babatunde Kassim Oladele

Data were collected using Stakeholders' suggested Strategies for fund prudent utilisation Interview and FGD schedules through physical visits to the various stakeholders. This was done through in-depth interviews with certain officers, while FGDs were used for collecting data from groups as much as feasible. Data collection lasted 25 working days in each state, while the resulting data were analysed using thematic qualitative analytical approach, after thematically coding them. The themes were derived from the broad categorization of as per the items on the instruments (FGD and interview schedules) and juxtaposed with the relevant responses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The data on this suggested model were generated through interview and focus group discussion sessions held with the participants comprising Council members/Principal Officers, Deans/Directors and Heads of Department, etc. Three main themes with their respective sub-themes emerged from the analysis of the ensuing data.

Theme 1: Consisted of Suggested strategies for prudent utilisation of funds

The data collected in this aspect of the study was done using Key Informant Interview (KII) and Focus Group Discussions (FGD). All the issues raised were analysed in themes. After the analysis, three basic themes emerged.

Theme 1.1: Accountability

In today's financial scenery, where stakeholders demand increased accountability, it becomes imperative for institutions to adopt robust strategies to ensure the proper management and utilisation of funds to attract sustainable funders. It entails evolving regular channel of communicating fund usage to the stakeholders as University of Ilorin does with IGR on regular basis (UIL Weekly Bulletin, February 26, 2024). To this end, a union leader suggested the evolution of a meticulous financial accountability reporting system to the Congregation on quarterly basis.

Theme 1.2: Financial transparency and Accountability

Stakeholders advocate transparent mechanism revolving around promoting openness, honesty, and clear communication regarding financial processes and decisions in NPHEIs. Hence, a union chairman emphasised the need for an established a meticulously open financial accountability system with transparently openness, because of the accessibility of financial records to all stakeholders. This underscores the necessity of transparency and responsibility in handling funds. In the participant's words, *"You account for every kobo even a pin, you must account for it everything, you need to account for it, so that's it."* (IP1: Union Chairman 2 of University1). There can be no accountability in the absence of transparency, thus the twin concepts go *pari pasu*.

Another participant advocated stakeholder involvement in institutional fund management.

According to this participant:

The involvement of stakeholders in the management of institutional funds would automatically encompass accountability and will definitely be of help, because one, like I keep telling people, if accountability is enthroned it will go a long way in curbing some of excesses, we have seen. There will be leadership in action (IP2: a Union Chairman, University 4)

A principal officer discussed the consequences of opaque spending processes, citing instances where lack of transparency led to fund mismanagement and subsequently crisis. The participant stressed the importance of accountability to ensure proper utilisation of funds and maintain credibility with funding bodies:

So, once the process of spending this money are not transparent, even the government sometimes, there was a time TETFund even stopped sending money to UNN because some people that go for research or people that collect the money for conferences, training or whatever have you, some people will collect the money and go back to their house and village and stay" (IP4: A Principal Officer, University 1)

A businessman underscored the importance of transparency in fund allocation and in expenditure to prevent corruption and ensure fairness. They suggested that transparency

promotes responsible financial decision-making and prevents misuse of funds: *"Transparency is good, because once there is transparency in how they spend the money, there will be liberality in terms of doing the things they are doing (IP1: Business man 2, University 2).*

Theme 2.1.: There should be financial discipline by institutional leadership

This theme refers to individual behaviours and practices that contribute to responsible financial management. A HoD in a university in a southern State acknowledged the dearth of some qualities in contemporary times, but advocated that institutional leaders utilise funds for institutional development for the benefit of the collective, rather than the satisfaction of personal interests, implying the spirit of selflessness and integrity (HoD, CoE 1).

Another staff, a management team member in the same institution pointed out the importance of utilising funds for their designated purposes, particularly those received from TETFund. This position indicates a commitment to financial transparency and accountability within the institution, ensuring that resources are expended on intended projects. According to this participant:

Well, for strategies, I suggest that the VC or the bursar may do that, but I know one of the things our VC insists on is that any money coming into the university or generated must utilized for the particular thing it is meant, for instance, when money comes from TETFund for a particular project it must not be utilized

for any other thing except what was meant for (IP3: A DAP, University1).

The participant further pointed out past financial practices where funds were pooled together and misappropriated leading to inefficiencies and crisis. However, the participant spoke of a concerted effort to track and earmark funds for specific projects under the institution's current administration, ensuring transparency and preventing misuse. He suggested thus:

If an agency makes a donation for a particular project, the fund just have to be used for it because in time past when the university had funds, they had a way of putting everything in one pool and sometimes depending on in the interest of the bursary, they may just use everything to pay contractors and when you now need money meant for another particular thing, they will tell you that there is no fund[chuckles] ...but one of the things that this administration does is to make sure that everything that comes in, the bursary keeps a tab on it, so that even when everything is in tears, they know that this is for this and it has to be used for that (IP3: DAP, University 5).

In a conversation at Polytechnic 3, a principal officer emphasised the importance of proactive maintenance of institutional property, suggesting a strategy to prevent deterioration and reduce long-term costs. This approach reflects a commitment to preserving resources and ensuring sustainability within the institution. According to the participant:

And then we also try to make ourselves realise that we have to have this attitude of trying to keep things that are polytechnic property, maintenance of polytechnic property. You know, you don't wait until something finally gets bad before you try to maintain it (IP4: Principal Officer, Polytechnic 3).

A lecturer in CoE No. 4 raised concerns about financial constraints and outstanding payments owed by the institution, "It is when we have excess that we can waste". The concern of the participant indicates the challenges faced in managing resources effectively, especially when dealing with existing personnel financial obligations and deductions.

These findings emphasise the potency of employing responsible financial practices: transparency, accountability and strategic prioritization of fund utilisation to address institutional needs and challenges effectively. These insights indicate a desire for prudent financial management within higher institutions despite various financial constraints and operational challenges.

Theme 1. 3 : Need for accountability further emphasised

This theme refers to the active promotion and implementation of practices and policies within the higher institutions of learning to prioritise and ensure clear responsibility, answerability, and transparency in financial management. A university student (FP1, University2) suggested that external auditing bodies, rather than internal audit units (which in reality are not

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quite independent of the Bursary), should oversee financial monitoring to ensure impartiality and prevent potential conflicts of interest. A reverend father from State 6 (IP2) highlighted some strategies for prudent fund utilisation, emphasising the importance of openness (transparency), accountability, and broad stakeholder involvement in financial decision-making processes.

This statement underscores the importance of ensuring that financial processes are not only in place but are also effectively communicated and adhered to, promoting accountability at all levels of the institution. A Principal Officer underscored the importance of regularly publishing financial statements to foster transparency and ensure accountability in university financial management. In his words:

And of course there's nothing wrong in, uh, we produce our financial statements every year and is published. He should. So, he's should there's not around there. Okay, sir, guys, thank you. You, we enjoy your..., you won't researching us, your men that are supporting you (IP2:36 Principal Officer, a University 5).

This statement emphasises the significance of regularly producing and publishing financial statements as a means of ensuring transparency and accountability. A union chairman linked the issue of accountability to resource scarcity within universities, suggesting that improved financial management can enhance educational outcomes:

That is the problem we have here, accountability because if there is a good accountability, I'm telling you, okay now can we ask ourselves this question, we don't have enough things to use to produce students and when we go outside, we compete with other students and we still did excellently well. So that means the missing link is not because people are not brilliant. It is the environment (IP9: Union chairman, University1).

This statement points out the fact that accountability is crucial in addressing challenges related to resource allocation and quality of education. It also suggests that effective accountability can lead to better resource utilisation, ultimately enhancing the learning environment and supporting students' academic success, due to the provision of conducive learning environment, a function of prudent utilisation of funds.

A lecturer from a CoE in State 4 spoke on the challenges of ensuring accountability in financial management within educational institutions, suggesting that sincerity among stakeholders is crucial for effective institutional financial governance:

.... How do we even monitor it? Well, I think yes ... mmh just like you said democracy takes its whole and the fear is always about accountability. If you have the stakeholders, having to maintain or handle the funds, well I wouldn't know because it is the same stakeholders that are also stakeholders in government directly or indirectly; and I think

Adams O.U. Onuka, Monica N. Odinko and Babatunde Kassim Oladele

they hold the funds somewhere too. So, I just believe that everything boils down to sincerity of persons (IP10: Lecturers, CoE 4, University 4 and Poly 4 in their various responses).

This statement underscores the challenges and complexities of monitoring financial accountability, especially in contexts where multiple stakeholders are involved in fund management. It highlights the need for sincerity and ethical conduct among those responsible for handling funds, as well as the importance of effective monitoring mechanisms to ensure transparency and prevent misuse of resources. These findings emphasise the interconnectedness of accountability, transparency, stakeholder involvement and ethical conduct in promoting responsible financial practices and effective governance within educational institutions.

Theme 2.1: Need for effective internal control system

This theme encompasses various strategies aimed at ensuring that financial resources are managed responsibly, ethically and in tandem with established guidelines. A principal officer emphasised the importance of implementing internal quality assurance measures and adhering to established accountability standards within universities: *“Internal quality assurance measures should be taken and established accountability standards observed.”* (IP1: Former Principal Officer, University 6).

A HoD suggested that the presence of checks and balances can help reduce corrupt practices, indicating the necessity for monitoring mechanisms to deter misuse of fund

There should always be a sort of check and balances. If there is check and balances, people will reduce their rate of, let me not say corruption, corrupted attitude. There should be that people that will even be checking even without them knowing that they are being checked monitoring (HoD, CoE 4).

A non-teaching staff proposed implementing an effective internal control system as a means to utilise available funds effectively, highlighting the importance of financial management mechanisms. According to this participant, *“By implementing an effective internal control system, this system can help us utilize the available funds effectively”* (IP2: Non-Teaching Staff, Polytechnic 3).

The participant mentioned the necessity for a control system to monitor the budget and track fund expenditure, underscoring the role of control mechanisms in ensuring effective fund utilisation: *“Also, the first type of control will monitor our budget and track how the funds are spent. This control system will monitor and supervise it, contributing to the effective utilisation of the funds”* - (IP2: Non-Teaching Staff, Polytechnic 3).

The participant explained the financial constraints in place, such as limits on cash advances, demonstrating a proactive approach to controlling expenditure and ensuring

financial discipline: *“Yes, we don’t spend money anyhow... she cannot approve more than 200 thousand... So, for instance this just concluded...”*. (IP6: HoD, University 1).

Overall, these findings emphasize the significance of internal controls, accountability standards, and proactive measures in promoting prudent fund utilisation, preventing financial misconduct, and upholding transparency and integrity in financial management within educational institutions.

Theme 2.2: Monitoring and supervision

Four sub-themes emerged under this suggestion.

Theme 2.2.1: Need for prudent financial practices

This theme focuses on promoting a shift in the mind-set and practices of people toward more prudent fund utilisation through effective monitoring and supervision in higher institutions. A former principal officer in a university in CoE in State 6 suggested that involving stakeholders in the mobilization and utilization of funds can lead to quality enhancement: *“Quality enhancement through stakeholders’ participation in mobilisation and utilisation of funds: rubrics for quality assurance and programme improvement”* (IP1: Former principal officer, university 6 and CoE 6). The view shared by the former principal emphasise the importance of collaboration and shared responsibility in ensuring effective prudent financial management.

Furthermore, the implementation of robust checks and balances to reduce corrupt practices was advocated by a HoD:

“There should always be a sort of check and balances. If there is check and balances, people will reduce their rate of, let me not say corruption, but corrupted attitude” (HoD, CoE 1).

The advocacy highlights the need for monitoring mechanisms to deter misconduct. Furthermore, the reduction of the appointment of politicians into administrative roles within higher institutions was suggested by a HoD to mitigate potential disruptive influences, advocating for a more academic-focused leadership. According to this HoD,

“And the state government should reduce appointment of politicians into not even in academics, into the board of higher institutions,... they are spoilers.... [frowns]... the need to appoint academics rather than politicians to administrative positions within institutions, “Why not appoint people in academics as board, as members of the council, as use members of academic will reduce most of those things” (HoD, CoE 1).

This suggestion believes that such approach can facilitate constructive dialogue and accountability. The tendency to prioritise expensive external contractors over utilising internal resources was criticised by a union chairman in a university in State 1 (IP2) *“Part of the problem is that even when the money comes, in order to please, quote and unquote,*

governments, they look for the so-called big-time contractors, foreign contractors...". This implies that leveraging internal expertise can lead to cost savings without compromising quality.

Similarly, the importance of accountability and sincerity among stakeholders in financial management was underscored by a lecturer in a CoE State 4 (IP10). In the participant's voice, *"How do we even monitor it? Well, I think... yes just like you said democracy takes its whole and the fear is always about accountability..."*. This response highlights the need for transparency and responsible handling of funds. In the same perspective, a Dean in a university in State 2 (IP15) criticised the lack of transparency in financial processes within universities, advocating for increased scrutiny and accountability to ensure adherence to agreements and standards.

These findings suggest the multifaceted approach required for prudent fund utilization, which includes stakeholder involvement, checks and balances, responsible leadership appointments, leveraging internal resources, and establishing robust monitoring mechanisms to ensure transparency and accountability in financial management within higher education institutions.

Theme 2.2.3: Effective funds management and record-keeping

This is a theme that emphasises the importance of systematic financial oversight and accurate

documentation in ensuring prudent fund utilization within higher education institutions. A university student in State 2 underscored the importance of proper management, supervision, and coordination in ensuring effective fund management:

"There must be proper management of which supervision and some other thing will involve... there must be coordination of different bodies that will be raised that okay to monitor this thing, to manage this thing time to time" **(IP14: University student in State 2).**

This view suggests that oversight and coordination among different bodies are crucial for successful financial management. A Dean in CoE, State 1 emphasised the importance of implementing checks and balances in spending to prevent unaccounted expenses, suggesting that establishing monitoring committees can significantly aid in controlling expenditure and ensuring accountability.

Further, a former principal officer suggested that involving stakeholders in the mobilization and utilization of funds can lead to quality enhancement: *"Quality enhancement through stakeholders' participation in mobilization and utilization of funds: rubrics for quality assurance and programme improvement"* **(IP1: Former Principal Officer, University, State 6).** This view implies that collaborative efforts can improve programme quality and ensure quality standards.

Theme 3.1: Effective monitoring committee

This theme revolves around the strategies and recommendations proposed by participants to ensure prudent fund utilization through effective project management and oversight mechanisms. The importance of planning, committee formation, and continuous monitoring to ensure the proper use of funds was emphasised by a principal officer (IP1) in a university in State 2. In the participant's words: *"For proper use of money, I think it's, first of all make plan for this yes, .. set up committee to check it and monitor it. Evaluation! Certainly yes."* Similarly, the necessity of establishing committees and working groups to expedite decision-making processes and ensure efficient use of resources was highlighted by a HoD in a polytechnic in State 5. According to the participant:

And the issue is that, like now the one we are doing is delaying because there is no strong force beside it, so we have to approach somebody's office without authority, so but if there is a committee and working senate, the management and some other set of people who are going to do the job they will be able to spare actions and get things done in a very short time.

The views of the participants suggest a structured approach to financial management and that formal structures facilitate timely actions. From the participant's viewpoint,

"There is no other way than to monitor that's monitoring committees, yes; stakeholders committee that would be ensuring that money budgeted for a specific task is actually used for this." This view advocates for accountability in financial management.

A unit coordinator in a polytechnic in State 3 described a concrete plan to ensure judicious spending on projects, highlighting the presence of monitoring teams and technical teams to oversee project execution. According to the participant,

"There's a concrete plan to ensure judicious spending on projects, with monitoring teams in place at the polytechnics, and members of technical teams and TETFund ensuring projects are carried out as planned." **(IP1: Unit Coordinator, Polytechnic 4).**

A student leader in a CoE in State 6 spoke about the strategies for prudent utilisation of funds: *"Strategies for prudent utilisation of funds: establish committees for procurement, accreditation, maintenance etc., in the Bursary Department."* (IP3: Student leader, in CoE 6). The mention of committees for procurement and accreditation under the Bursary Department suggests a structured approach to financial management and reinforces the importance of structured oversight in financial matters. By assigning specific responsibilities to committees, the institution aims to ensure efficiency, transparency, streamline processes, and promote accountability in fund management and compliance with regulatory

Adams O.U. Onuka, Monica N. Odinko and Babatunde Kassim Oladele

requirements. A call for the formation of a supervisory committee to monitor spending by a Dean in a CoE 1 called highlights the necessity for checks and balances within educational institutions. In his words:

“I suggest that there should be checks and balances, a supervisory committee has to be set that will monitor the spending. There is every need for that to be done for accountability, so every kobo that is allotted for every project has to be accounted for so there is a need for that particular supervisory body to take that particular responsibility (IP2, Dean in a CoE 1)”

Advocating transparency and accountability in financial matters aims to ensure that allocated funds are expended appropriately on the projects, they were designated for. A student in a university in State 2 called for the establishment of committees to oversee research funding. This suggestion indicates the recognition of the importance of effective resource allocation and utilisation to the pursuit of academic undertakings:

I think there should be a committee. I think a committee should be set up to go through the various faculties and departments. This is so, especially, in those departments that deal directly with the researches. Of course, the researches would require funding; I believe if those committees would be able to get the possibilities and output of those researches, encourage the process, I think that will go a

long way to ensure further inflow of funds (FP3: Student, University, State 2).

By proposing dedicated committees, the participant wants institutions to ensure that research projects receive adequate support and oversight in order to maximise their impact. Likewise, a lecturer in a CoE in one of the States in the North (IP5) proposed establishment of a committee to include representatives from the immediate community of the institutions to underscore the importance of community engagement in financial decision-making processes: *“A committee should be set up to include community representatives. Before we can take on any of this work, you must give a signature of the account”*. By incorporating diverse stakeholders, institutions will promote transparency and accountability in fund utilisation. This is in conformity with findings of Onuka (2012) with respect to funding research undertaking.

Theme 3.2.3: Holistic stakeholders' involvement in funds management

The theme emphasises the importance of engaging various stakeholders to oversee the management of financial resources within higher education institutions. For example, a former principal officer emphasised quality enhancement through stakeholder participation in funds management. According to the participant, *“Quality enhancement through stakeholders' participation in mobilization and utilization of funds: rubrics for quality assurance and programme improvement”*

(IP1: Former principal officer, University 6).

One of the Deans in a university in State 2 recommended involvement of stakeholders in fund management with emphasis on setting up panels, *“To me, all stakeholders should be involved in utilising the money. A panel should be set up or a committee to monitor all spending pertaining to universities”* **(IP4: Dean, University 2)**. The recommendation for stakeholder involvement and the establishment of monitoring committees reflects a commitment to ensuring accountability and prudent utilisation of funds. By engaging all stakeholders in implementing oversight measures, the institution would aim at preventing mismanagement and promote financial integrity. This is in consonance with the finding of kasozi (2009) that fund utilisation must be for public good.

The importance of stakeholder involvement in monitoring and evaluation was highlighted by a HoD to prevent fund diversion and ensure accountability. By advocating for regular reporting and updating of accounts, the institution aims to enhance transparency and prevent financial mismanagement. According to the participant:

I think it's important because when this money is made available and there is no monitoring on evaluation, it becomes a problem. So, there is need for the stakeholders to be involved, at least giving quarterly report and then

updating of account. We will also help in making sure that these funds are not diverted to private pockets **(IP8: HoD, University 1)**

Furthermore, a Dean noted that in principle, stakeholders who contribute financially have a legitimate right in monitoring how such funds are utilised. According to him:

If you are contributing and I am contributing and you want to know how the money is being used, I think you should be allowed. There is no way you will be throwing in your money into something and then you will not be interested in how it is used, so stakeholders has the right to participate and to get involved in monitoring how funds are used only if they are contributing something **(IP15: Dean, University 2)**.

The statement suggests that involvement in funding gives stakeholders the right to participate in oversight processes to ensure transparency and accountability in financial management, thus agreeing with the submission of Onuka (2017) and Kasozi (2009) on the need for stakeholders' involvement in fund utilisation public tertiary education institutions for public good. The overall findings highlight the critical role of stakeholder involvement in ensuring prudent fund utilization and effective financial management within higher education institutions.

The overall evolved utilisation model based on suggestions by the stakeholders is presented in

Figure 1.

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Adams O.U. Onuka, Monica N. Odinko and Babatunde Kassim Oladele

Figure 1. The Derived NPHEIs Stakeholders’ Fund Utilisation Model

Adams O.U. Onuka, Monica N. Odinko and Babatunde Kassim Oladele

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Discussion

The results presented here showcases the various approaches, practices and considerations suggested by stakeholders to be used in prudently managing financial resources efficiently within the context of Nigerian public higher education institutions. To ensure prudent spending of the available funds, participants suggested ways to ensure effective management of funds. These various approaches and practices that higher institutions, which could be used to ensure efficient and effective use of funds including advocacy for effective internal control system, transparency, accountability, personal discipline, prudent practices, monitoring and supervision, funds management and record-keeping, and stakeholders' involvement in funds management. In the context of prudent fund utilisation within higher institutions, discipline and transparency emerged as a fundamental strategy guiding financial management practices. These practices, according to the respondents, are essential for ensuring accountability, integrity and responsible stewardship of financial resources. The following practices were suggested by the participants: mechanisms for personal financial discipline, prudent spending, transparency and judicious use of resources should be adopted strategy for prudent fund utilisation in NPHEIs. This observation is in tandem with the observation of Oralu and Babatunde (2015 and 2016) to extent that corporate monitoring of

fund utilisation is germane to prudent fund management.

The suggested strategies for prudent utilisation of funds also included: presenting actionable guidelines aimed at promoting efficient and responsible funds management within higher institutions. Certainly, ensuring that an institution appropriately applied funds is very pivotal to the success of such institution. It is also important to explain how those funds are dispensed internally and aligned with overall strategic objectives. It is the duty of the administration to build trust amongst their academic and non-academic community or risk the challenges that comes from mismanagement of funds. There must be a trust and that trust is dependent on establishing and building confidence through transparency and accountability. Thus, to create such trust, those entrusted with the funds should create avenues to intimate the benefactors with how the funds entrusted to the institution's administration are utilised. This again confirm the findings of Onuka (2012 and 2017) that involvement of stakeholders in fund utilisation oversight will build the confidence of stakeholders in institutional funding. The finding also corroborates the recommendation by Nabena, Eze, Rowe, Mohammed and Oni (2024) that efficiency of allocated resource to the education sector in Nigeria can be ensured through transparency, accountability and fiscal discipline.

Adams O.U. Onuka, Monica N. Odinko and Babatunde Kassim Oladele

Another strategy advocated by the respondents is the practice of transparency and accountability. **Accountability** consists of responsibility, explicability or answerability for ones stewardship to those who have entrusted them with public good (in any work category). In the context of education, fiscal accountability is a quest for efficiency in the use of funds for their intended purposes. Here efficiency means a demand that public money should not be wasted through fraudulent acts or through misapplication. Accountability also implies the responsibility and obligation of the public to provide necessary supports, financial and moral for the provision of functional education. Respondents argued that in contemporary financial landscape, as stakeholders demand increased transparency and accountability, it becomes imperative that institutions should adopt robust strategies to ensure proper management and utilisation of funds. For instance, a student leader emphasised the importance of accountability in student governance, suggesting that student representatives should report back to their constituencies to enhance transparency and ensure judicious financial administration. In his words:

For proper accountability, officials in SUG should report back to their constituencies. Students' representation should increase for judicious financial administration to enhance transparency and subsequently, accountability (IP3: A Key student leader, CoE 6).

Another participant advocated stakeholder involvement in fund management, underscoring that involving stakeholders will help in curbing excessive spending. This suggests that an accountable leadership foster a culture of public service for public good, promoting responsible financial practices. Also, a union chairman stressed the necessity for accountability in preventing misconduct and ensuring the effective utilisation of funds. According to him: *"We have a culture that if people... if there is no regulatory or monitoring body, people tend to allow themselves to be over tempted, so we need accountability mechanism if we must get it right."* (IP9: Union Chairman, University 1). The interviewee emphasised the importance of maintaining accurate financial records and adhering to designated fund usage. In another participant's words:

The banking mechanism should be there, when money is received let the institution know that money is received and when money is spent, let them know for what purpose, ... Account should be kept and made available for public use (IP9: Student, University 2).

All these statements show that accountability fosters trust and encourages sincerity in fund management. Advocacy for accountability is a means to uphold integrity and honesty in financial management. Respondents argue that without transparency, funds can be misappropriated, leading to distrust and confusion among stakeholders. They suggest that transparency promotes responsible

financial decision-making and prevents misuse of funds, and, therefore, accountability. These findings underscore the importance of instilling a culture of transparency, accountability and responsible financial stewardship within educational institutions to maintain credibility, prevent misuse of funds and foster trust among stakeholders. Thereby making it imperative an evolved prudent stakeholders' participation in fund utilisation model in our Public higher education institutions as in Figure 1 above, which proposes three principal themes for stakeholders' involvement: Transparency and Accountability Mechanism; Monitoring and supervision Mechanism and Mechanism for handlers' personal financial discipline. These submissions are in consonance with those of earlier studies that fiscal accountability is a tool for sustainable fund provision by institution's stakeholders (Bamiro and Adedeji, 2010, Onuka, 2012; 2017; Kasozi, 2009; Ayodele, 2025).

The necessity for using monitoring and supervision committees comprising of stakeholders to ensure appropriate use of allocated funds was suggested. According to one of the Deans in a polytechnic in State 1, "*There is no other way than to constitute monitoring committees, yes, stakeholders committee that would be ensuring that money budgeted for a specific task is actually used for this*". Such suggestion highlights the importance of establishing robust mechanisms to oversee financial activities, track fund allocation and

expenditure and to ensure that resources are responsibly and effectively utilised. Under these strategies, it was advocated that prudent practices and record-keeping could ensure appropriate fund utilisation. For prudent practices, the stakeholders advocated the use of effective monitoring and supervision, involving stakeholders in the utilization of funds and invariably, in fund mobilisation. The mechanism for prudent fund utilisation should contain robust checks and balances. They also advocated reduction of the appointment of politicians into administrative roles in these institutions, requesting for a more academic-focused leadership, utilising internal contractors, increased scrutiny and accountability as well as having responsible leadership in place. This supports the recommendation of Onuka (2012) that frivolities should be eliminated from the spending of the Nigerian Public system and Oduwaiye's (2014) and Ayodele's (2025) observation that financial administration efficiency will be improved with an improved monitoring system in place.

A union Chairman in a State Polytechnic advocated for participatory budgeting and the establishment of a budget monitoring committee to enhance transparency and accountability in fund management. The suggestion shows a recognition of the importance of stakeholder involvement in financial decision-making processes, which could lead to improved budgetary outcomes and

increased public trust. According to the participant:

...most of the time you see things happening not even at the school level but even at the governmental level because they are not participating that is why you see most of the time the target is not met so if there is participatory budgeting, we draw budget monitoring committee that will monitor and will be empower to monitor the process of the budget money up to the finalization of the process I think they will be a lot of achievement

(IP1: Union Chairman Polytechnic 2)

The stakeholders' suggestion for funds management and record-keeping stresses the importance of systematic financial oversight and accurate documentation in ensuring prudent fund utilization within higher education institutions and also indicates the importance of internal mechanisms such as transparent auditing to ensure accountability in fund management. These statements were revealed in the following accounts:

[1]: Proper record keeping, I think is very important sir. Yeah! In managing funds, yes (IP13: Student, University 2).

[2]: There are some internal mechanisms which should be in place. Let's look at the audit, for instance. There should be proper auditing of money that comes in, that goes out, and on what those funds are expended" (IP19: Non-Teaching, CoE 3).

The significance of stakeholders' involvement in fund management was linked to ensuring

accountability and integrity as well as to curb excesses, according to a union chairman:

The involvement of stakeholders in the management of the funds that they gave for instance asking for accountability will definitely be of help because one, like I keep telling people, if accountability is enthroned it will go a long way in curbing some of the excesses, we have, see leadership is service **(IP2: Union Chairman, University 1).**

Maintaining accountability, and viewing leadership as a service, will promote transparency and responsible financial stewardship. Based on logic, by encouraging stakeholders to contribute to funding and oversee its utilisation, the institutions will be promoting transparency, accountability and integrity through adherence to financial operations' objectives.

In the same vain, another union chairman underscored the need for stakeholders to actively participate in funding and monitoring educational systems to ensure that investments and fund utilisation align with institutional goals:

So, instead of allowing funding to remain a challenge, they would also come in and contribute to the funding as much as they are of part of the monitoring of the system, because you don't invest and you turn your back on your investment, you need to make sure that the purpose is achieved without deviating from it and there is no mix up anywhere **(IP9: Union Chairman, a University 1).**

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Also, a lecturer in a CoE in State 4 (IP10: Lecturer, CoE 4) reflected on the challenges of monitoring funds and highlighted the importance of stakeholder sincerity in financial management. The participant was of the view that accountability relies on the integrity of individuals involved, including stakeholders with direct or indirect ties to the government. The implication is that genuine commitment to transparency and honesty is essential for effective fund management.

A lecturer from a CoE in State 4 expressed concern over the misuse of TETFund grants by some lecturers and suggested establishing internal checks to prevent such occurrences:

Very common that many of us, many lecturers collect TETFund grant and then just take the money and spent it without doing all the necessary things. I was on a TETFund project where some malfeasance took place, I would have submitted all their names but it will embarrass the college. So that is why we are now putting up internal machinery to check such excesses (IP9: Lecturer, CoE 4)

This contribution is recognition of the importance of accountability in the utilisation of external grants, such as TETFund grants. The mention of internal machinery for checks outlines the institution's commitment to ensuring that funds are used for their intended purposes. This reflects a proactive stance against potential misuse of external funds and a commitment to maintaining integrity in financial management practices.

These responses collectively emphasise the importance of establishing monitoring committees, engaging stakeholders, and implementing robust oversight mechanisms to ensure prudent utilisation of funds within higher educational institutions. The findings also suggest that proper oversight and documentation are crucial for accountability, for tracking income and expenditure and maintaining detailed records. This confirms the position of Aregbeyen (2025), Ayeni (2025) and Olatunji and Onuka (2024) that academic units' and other stakeholders' involvement in deciding how available funds would be distributed among the institutions' component-users would minimise financial leakages, as was reportedly done in Makerere University in Kampala, Uganda (Onen, 2024). Furthermore, participants suggested stakeholders' involvement in funds management in NPHEIs. This emphasis implies recognition of the importance of collaborative efforts in mobilising and utilising funds for educational improvement. By involving stakeholders in quality assurance and programme enhancement, institutions would be ensuring that transparency, accountability and ultimately, the enhancement of educational standards through prudent fund administration. The bottom line of all these observations conform with advocacy that African public tertiary education system should evolve sustainable funding model for their improvement, which prudent fund utilisation

Adams O.U. Onuka, Monica N. Odinko and Babatunde Kassim Oladele

model would enhance as were revealed by studies conducted in Nigeria, Kenya, Uganda and Ghana (Daku, 2009; Okebukola, 2015; Kiamba, 2015; Bakkabulindi, 2005; Newman & Duwiejua, 2015;).

CONCLUSION

The crux of this study is to derive a sustainable stakeholders' participation in fund utilisation in the Nigerian public higher institutions. Thus, study elicited various stakeholders' submission on how best they could participate in fund utilisation, since they are expected to be involved in mobilising funds for these institutions, as it became obvious the governments at both sub-national and national levels cannot sustainably keep these institutions meeting their goals, considering the paucity of funds in the system. A three principal-component fund utilisation model was derived from the stakeholders' submissions. The model hereby tagged sustainable NPHEIs utilisation stakeholder-participation model: Mechanisms for 1. Transparency and Accountability:- Transparency, Accountability and Effective Internal Control; 2. Mechanism for Monitoring through mechanisms for prudent practices, fund management and transparent record-keeping, stakeholder-participation in fund management and monitoring committees; 3. Institutional fund handlers' personal financial discipline and integrity mechanisms. In summary, the Proposed NPHEIs' stakeholders' fund utilisation model consists of three proposed main mechanisms: Prudent financial

practices mechanism to outline guidelines for stakeholders' involvement in ensuring prudent financial practices in the NPHEIs including budgeting; Mechanism for stakeholder-participation in fund management in the system and Mechanism for stakeholder involvement in monitoring fund utilisation and specified in the budget. Stakeholders believe that if these suggestions are implemented there will be a lot of improvement in stakeholders' fund mobilisation efforts to improve the quality of education being provided by the NPHEIs. A stakeholders' summit should examine and adapt the model for implementation to ensure sustainable funding for NPHEIs. The proposed model suggests that component-fund-users within the system should be involved in deciding the spending pattern among units for ease of monitoring for accountability.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Arising from the findings and conclusion derived from this study, the following suggestions were made:

1. The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND), the sponsors of the research project, should as a matter of urgency, present the report to the Federal Ministry of Education to study it and present it to stakeholders in the education industry for further scrutiny and adaptation.
2. State Ministries of Education should key into the final model for seamlessly funding of NPHEIs for quality education output
3. The finally adapted version should be used

by all public higher education institutions in Nigeria to guide their financial operations for transparency, accountability and integrity to earn public confidence and also earn the goodwill that will ensure sustainably inflow of stakeholders' financial contributions to ensure quality outputs from our high citadels of learning. This should be done through stakeholders' summit and subsequently backed up by legislation to ensure strict implementation.

4. Quantitative approach should be also engaged as way of confirming the outcome of this qualitative approach to make its implementation more seamless.
5. Decision on fund usage should be made in collaboration component-fund-users within the system to ensure prudence, transparency and accountability.
6. Duplication in functions should be eliminated by revisiting governance structure of NPHEIs, to ensure prudence in fund utilisation as well as personal fiscal discipline and responsibility should be encouraged.

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